

ADMINISTRATIVE BEHAVIOUR AMONG THE HIGHER SECONDARY TEACHERS

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Abstract:

School is the miniature society where the future of the country is build. Schools are one of the prime concerns of the whole educational process. Effective leadership is the key factor of the success of any educational institutions. The success and development of the school mostly depends upon the administrative behaviour of the teachers who is the hub of the entire educational institution. The development of the school depends on the nature and quality of leadership, management and administrative behaviour exhibited by the head of the institution. Without principal's effort school cannot bring any changes. The teachers play an important role in planning processes of the school. The systematic planning of material and non- material resources of the school by the teachers beforehand will decide the success of the school. So it is very necessary to study teachers' administrative behaviour in the area of planning for the success of the school.

Key Words: Administrative Behaviour and Higher Secondary School Teachers

Need for the Study:

The teachers of the school may be considered as the solar orbit round whom all the student planets revolve. The students correspond to the army, the staff to the body of officers, campus corresponds to the territory. While comparing, Ryburn compares the teachers to the captain of a ship, who like the captain in the ship, holds the key position in the school. A teacher holds the key position in the school. He is the hub of the school activity. He draws the whole plan of the school, execute the plan, and distribute work and co-ordinates the activities. He ensures smooth functioning and harmonious development of the whole school programme. The success of the school system depends upon their efficiency, alertness, sagacity, imagination, originality and experience. Their personality carts a strong formidable impact on the school programme. The success of any organisation depends on its level of performance. In case of school as an organisation, its success depends specifically on students' performance. Though society is demanding better education in terms of quality teaching and education for all students, many students still do not receive education that helps them reach their full potential, regardless of the reforms and efforts aimed at promoting student achievement. This at least in part can attribute to lack of effective leadership focused on teaching and learning. To raise the level of student performance the administrators, the school leader, and teachers should take responsibility. The responsibility of the administrators is to develop vision of education, plan, organise, determine the objectives, manage the schedule, monitor the budget, ensure safety etc., Where as the Principal's job is to monitor priorities like developing the organisation's vision, maintaining the timetable schedule, and ensuring the school buses run on time, responsibilities of the teachers on the whole is to increase the success level of their students.

Terms and Definitions:

Administrative Behaviour: "influence procedure moving the elucidation of measures for the school to motivate to the teachers and students to achieve the objectives and the maintenance of cooperative relationships and team work"

Higher Secondary Teachers "those who are handling XI and XII standard students in Madurai district".

Dependent Variable: Administrative behaviour

Independent Variables

- Gender : Male/Female
- Nativity : Rural / Urban
- Major subject : Arts/Science

Aims:

- To assess the altitude of administrative behavior among the higher secondary teachers.
- To locate whether there is significant differences in administrative behavior among the higher secondary teachers in terms of select independent variables viz. gender, nativity and major subjects.

Hypotheses:

- Administrative behaviour among the higher secondary teachers are above average.
- Gender exerts a significant influence on administrative behavior among the higher secondary teachers.
- Nativity exerts a significant influence on administrative behavior among the higher secondary teachers.

- Major subject exerts a significant influence on administrative behaviour among the higher secondary teachers.

Sample: A random sample of 310 secondary school teachers in Madurai district.

Tools Used: Administrative Behaviour Schedule by Sthiyagirirajan, S (2003).

Statistical Treatment: 't'- test

Studies Related to Administrative Behaviour:

Bulach (2001) working with Corvers of the Louisiana Department of Education, investigated the relationship of a school's culture and climate to the principal's leadership style. Six Louisiana schools participated in the study. The two schools with the best culture and climate scores also had the highest scores on the Supervisory Climate Survey, and the two with the lowest scores on culture and climate also had the lowest scores on the Supervisory Climate Survey.

Khan (2002) in his study on leadership roles and improvement of standard of education in Pakistan found lack of communication and friction among staff, political pressure, substandard equipment, curricular and co-curricular activities, centralization of power, lack of proper supervision, lack of cooperation from localities, unsatisfactory instructional material. It was revealed that senior heads in age are less flexible and more effective in their assigned work. The study also explored that the heads with higher professional qualifications are more efficient. The study further indicated that the performance of the teachers of those institutions where school heads applied sharing leadership style was significantly higher than those of the teachers working under the other leadership style i.e. telling, selling and delegating.

Hypotheses Verification:

Hypothesis 1: Administrative behaviour among the higher secondary teachers is low

The average score of the Administrative behaviour among the higher secondary teachers is 123.65, while the theoretical average is 105. **Hence the hypothesis 1 is accepted.**

Hypothesis 2: Gender exerts a significant influence on administrative behaviour among the higher secondary teachers.

Table 1: Statistical measures of administrative behaviour and Gender

Variable	Sub-category	N	M	S.D	't'-value	Significance at 0.05 level
Gender	Male	115	119.86	26.77	-1.982	Significant
	Female	195	125.89	25.79		

This shows that there is a significant difference between the male and female students in terms of administrative behaviour among the higher secondary teachers. Further, it is observed that female teachers have high administrative behaviour than male teachers. Hence the hypothesis 2 is accepted.

Hypothesis 3: Nativity exerts a significant influence on administrative behaviour among the higher secondary teachers

Table 2: Statistical measures of administrative behaviour and Nativity

Variable	Sub-category	N	M	S.D	't'-value	Significance at 0.05 level
Nativity	Rural	232	122.71	27.19	-1.075	Not Significant
	Urban	78	126.49	25.96		

This shows that there is no significant difference between rural and urban teachers in terms of administrative behaviour. Further, it is observed that nativity does not influence on administrative behaviour among teachers. Hence the hypothesis 2 is rejected.

Hypothesis 4: Major subject exerts a significant influence on administrative behaviour among the higher secondary teachers

Table 3: Statistical measures of administrative behaviour and Major Subject

Variable	Sub-category	N	M	S.D	't'-value	Significance at 0.05 level
Major subject	Arts	230	124.92	26.09	1.478	Not Significant
	Science	80	119.75	26.64		

This shows that there is no significant difference between arts and science teachers in terms of administrative behaviour. Further, it is observed that major subject does not influence on administrative behaviour among teachers. Hence the hypothesis 3 is rejected.

Conclusions

The major conclusions arrived at from the study are listed below:

- Administrative behaviour among higher secondary teachers is found high.
- Administrative behaviour among higher secondary teachers is found dependent on Gender
- Administrative behaviour among higher secondary teachers is found independent upon- Nativity and Major subject

Educational Implications:

The present study aimed to know the higher secondary teachers Administrative behaviour. In fact teaching line is a mission to make dignity and prestige of this job, every teaching staff, authorities, administrative authorities employers should try their best. The future of every nation is depended on teaching institute. For the diagnose of this problem until the environment of love, friendship among them will not create, till then the development of education would not be possible, so that to renounce the politics, teachers should ready to obey order and have feelings of discipline and helping nature for their head master. So that the environment of education should be full of dignity and united with prestige for making the educational environment according to the hope and desire of our society. In this direction, role of teachers and professors are important because these persons play an important role in the creation of educational environment.

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